

Studies on the Dissociation Constants and Solubilities of Amino Acids in Ethylene Glycol + Water Mixtures

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Manuscript received 18 February 1993, revised 7 December 1993, accepted 9 December 1993

The dissociation constant and solubility of a number of amino acids have been determined pH-metrically and spectrophotometrically in ethylene glycol (EG) + water mixtures at 298 K. The free energies of transfer of amino acids from water to mixed solvents, thus obtained, have been coupled with the free energies of transfer [ΔG_t^0 (1) and ΔG_t^0 (2)] for the reactions $\text{RH}_2^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{RH}^+ + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ \dots (1)$ and $\text{RH}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{R}^- + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ \dots (2)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ values determined in our laboratory to get the free energies of transfer of RH_2^+ and R^- in different mixed solvents. These give the quantitative measures of ion-solvent interactions of the zwitterions, cations and anions of the amino acids. The results have been discussed in terms of structural changes of solvent mixtures resulting in the change in acid-base properties and solute-solvent interactions. A critical assessment has been made regarding the determination of single ion values.

Solubilities of amino acids and glycine peptides in different solvent media were studied by Nozaki and Tanford¹ to provide a rational explanation for the ability of various solvent media to promote protein denaturation and allow quantitative predictions of relative denaturing capability of different solvents with respect to water. Moreover, solubility measurements have been utilised by them to have a semiquantitative estimate of interactions inside the native protein molecule for hydrophobic moieties relative to the interaction of the same moieties when exposed to water and thus establish a hydrophobicity scale for hydrophobic side chains.

We are, however, interested in the determination of the free energies of transfer for the dissociation of organic acids particularly the biologically important amino acids, the basic structural units of proteins. However, as pointed out by Popovych and Tomkins², the thermodynamic transfer functions for electrolytes give scanty information regarding solvent effects on the solute-solvent interactions and structural variations in these solvents, better information can be obtained from the transfer free energies of single ions. In most cases the single ion values are limited to inorganic ions but the determination of single ion values of

organic ions are of great relevance because of their predominant utility in living systems. The dissociation constants and solubility of the amino acids would be absolutely essential for the determination of the single values of the amino acids.

The aspects of the solvent effects of mono-ol + water mixtures on the dissociation and solvation processes of the amino acids have been studied in our laboratory³⁻⁷. Studies have been extended to determine the dissociation constants and solubilities of some important amino acids (glycine, α -alanine, L-leucine, L-valine, L-serine, L-glutamine, L-phenylalanine, L-methionine, L-asparagine and L-proline) in ethylene glycol + water mixtures which we report in the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

The free energy of transfer of amino acids from water to mixed solvents have been calculated using the relation,

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{RH}^\pm) = -RT \ln \frac{S_c}{W_c} - RT \ln \frac{S_f}{W_f} \quad (1)$$

where, S_c , W_c , S_f and W_f represent the molar concentrations and activity coefficients of amino

acids in the mixed solvents and water respectively. The activity coefficients of amino acids in EG + H₂O mixtures are not known and difficult to determine. However, we consider the method of activity corrections as done by Nozaki and Tanford¹ (followed by Talukdar and coworkers⁸) is of little relevance and introduce uncertainties.

The activity of amino acids in water were determined using isopiestic method⁹ where the equilibrium activities of water in the sucrose solutions (determined from freezing point or osmotic pressure measurements) were equated to the equilibrium activities of water in amino acid solutions. It is obvious that vapour pressures of the amino acids in mixed solvents can not be the same as those in water containing the same molality of amino acids. Moreover, if the equilibrium vapour pressure be the basis for activity coefficient determination, then further corrections for solute-solute interactions of amino acids (assumed to be chiefly electrostatic) involving the multiplications of $RT \ln S_i$ by ϵ_w/ϵ_s (ϵ_w and ϵ_s are the dielectric constants of water and mixed solvent respectively) become redundant. The expression for the activity coefficient of amino acids in presence of salts derive by Kirkwood¹⁰ is

$$-\log f = \frac{A}{\epsilon^2 T^2} (R^2/a)\mu$$

(a is the mean distance of closest approach of the ions of the salts to the dipolar ion and R is the distance between the charges of the dipolar ion), i.e. $\log f$ terms are inversely proportional to ϵ^2 .

Due to enormous decrease in solubility of amino acids in mixed solvents, electrostatic interactions can be assumed to be small and Nozaki and Tanford considered electrostatic interactions are not of prime importance in case of amino acids other than glycines. We, therefore, report the free energy of transfer as

$$\Delta G_i^\circ (\text{RH}^\pm) = -RT \ln \frac{S_{c_i}}{W_{c_i}} \quad (2)$$

assuming the activity coefficients of amino acids to be unity in the corresponding states of saturated solution in the respective solvents.

The acidic and basic dissociation equilibria of the amino acids can be represented by equations (3) and (4),

and

The equations (3) and (4) can be written as

$$\text{p}K_1 = \text{pH} - \log \left(\frac{C}{a - C_{\text{H}^+}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{f_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \quad (5a)$$

$$= B + \log U_{\text{H}} - \log \left(\frac{C}{a - C_{\text{H}^+}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{f_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \quad (5b)$$

and

$$\text{p}K_2 = \text{pH} + \log \left(\frac{C}{b - C_{\text{OH}^-}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \quad (6a)$$

$$= B' + \log U_{\text{H}} + \log \left(\frac{C}{b - C_{\text{OH}^-}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \quad (6b)$$

Equations 5a, 6a and 5b, 6b correspond to aqueous and mixed solvents respectively, where, C is the concentration of neutral amino acid, a or b the concentration of acid or base respectively, and C_{H^+} or C_{OH^-} the concentration of H^+ ion or OH^- ion in the experimental solution (determined pH-metrically). The appropriate corrections ($\log U_{\text{H}}$) were made for pH-meter readings B and B' in the mixed solvents using the well-known method described earlier¹¹⁻¹⁶. The values of autoprotolysis constants of H_2O in EG + H_2O (upto 58.2)¹⁷ were taken into consideration in calculating C_{OH^-} in mixed solvents.

The concentrations of amino acids and HClO_4 or NaOH used are $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ and 3.0-7.0

$\times 10^{-3}$ M respectively. f_{H^+} and f_{R^-} can be fairly accurately calculated in dilute solutions using Davies equation¹⁸,

$$-\log f_{\pm} = \frac{AZ_+ Z_- \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.2\mu \quad (7)$$

The activity coefficients of amino acids in mixed solvents have been assumed to be unity in the concentration ranges studied. However, in case of pK_1 , the effect would be only marginal as f_{H^+} and $f_{RH_2^+}$ cancel each other but the deviations

may be considerable in case of pK_2 . The free energies of transfer for the first and second dissociation of amino acids have been calculated using equations (8) and (9),

$$\Delta G_t^\circ(1) = 2.303 RT [pK_s(1) - pK_w(1)] \quad (8)$$

and

$$\Delta G_t^\circ(2) = 2.303 RT [pK_s(2) - pK_w(2)] \quad (9)$$

The solubility values of amino acids in EG + H₂O mixtures (Table 1) agree well with the literature values¹⁹. Most of the amino acids are related and obtained by the replacement of H atom of glycine and alanine by CH₃, CH(CH₃)₂, CONH₂, OH, CH₂SCH₃, C₆H₅ etc. The solubility values in water can be arranged as glycine > α -alanine > L-valine > L-serine > L-glutamine > L-asparagine > L-methionine > L-leucine > L-phenylalanine, though the sequence changes in mixed solvents. The decrease in solubility of amino acids increases with increase in hydrophobic characters of the groups present in amino acids as

well as with the hydrophobic character of the solvent mixtures, i.e. the solubility sequence is EG + H₂O > methanol + water > ethanol + water > isopropanol + H₂O > t-butanol + H₂O mixtures. However, it is not possible to compare the solubility values of the amino acids (molar units) determined by us in mixed solvents (w/w) with those reported by Nozaki and Tanford¹ at 25.1 in 30, 60 and 90% of solvent mixtures (v/v) (in g/100 g of solvent) but the trend indicates that the results are in the right order of magnitude.

The changes in solubility sequence of the amino acids in H₂O and EG + H₂O mixtures can be attributed to specific solvation (or hydrophilic) and hydrophobic interactions which though acting in the opposite direction complete for water structure organisation^{20,21}. The hydrophobic effect increases with the increase in the size of the solute and is maximum where maximum enhancement of the water-structure occurs, i.e. in the region of 0.3 mole fraction of EG. The increased size of the hydrophobic group shifts the point of maximum structure formation towards media rich in water. Specific solvation effects are dependent mainly on the composition of the solvent-mixture, being greatest for strongly solvated amino acids. Thus above 20% EG, L-asparagine becomes least soluble usually followed by L-glutamine. Above 90% EG, solubility of alanine is greater than that of glycine. The pK_1 and pK_2 values at 298 K determined in EG + H₂O mixtures are recorded in Table 2.

Since we are particularly interested to study

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY (mol dm⁻³) OF AMINO ACIDS IN DIFFERENT EG + H₂O MIXTURES AT 298 K

Wt% of EG	Glycine	α -Alanine	L-Valine	L-Serine	L-Glutamine	L-Asparagine	L-Methionine	L-Leucine	L-phenylalanine
0 0	3 325	1 865	0 754	0 472	0 264	0 230	0 229	0 184	0 180
11 03	2 450	1 560	0 560	0 295	0 189	0 152	0 145	0 151	0 128
21 80	1 650	1 440	0 344	0 243	0 164	0 071	0 132	0 138	0 078
32 34	1 220	0 905	0 275	0 210	0 127	0 041	0 114	0 123	0 069
42 65	1 050	0 483	0 230	0 171	0 099	0 027	0 099	0 068	0 042 5
52 73	0 655	0 425	0 170	0 143	0 089	0 016 1	0 091 5	0 061	0 034 3
62 59	0 470	0 335	0 128	0 121	0 069 2	0 011 2	0 082 0	0 054	0 028 3
72 24	0 345	0 270	0 104	0 097	0 038 0	0 008 2	0 078 0	0 047	0 019 0
81 69	0 178	0 166	0 090	0 072 9	0 012 6	0 005 1	0 054 7	0 034	0 014 0
90 94	0 106	0 110	0 068	0 059 5	0 008 7	0 003 1	0 021 9	0 022	0 011 0
100 00	0 046	0 094	0 020	0 031 0	0 004 9	0 001 2	0 009 8	0 016	0 006 0

TABLE 2—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF AMINO ACIDS (IN TERMS OF pK_1 AND pK_2) IN DIFFERENT EG + H₂O MIXTURES

Wt% of EG	$1/\epsilon \times 10^2$	L-Valine		L-Asparagine		L-Serine		L-Glutamine		L-Methionine		L-Proline		
		pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	
0.0	1.27	2.33	9.64	2.09	8.73	2.21	9.07	2.18	9.10	2.29	9.20	2.01	10.60	
11.03	1.33	2.47	9.66	2.26	8.75	2.35	9.08	2.40	9.11	2.39	9.21	2.14	10.64	
21.80	1.39	2.59	9.68	2.40	8.79	2.43	9.10	2.46	9.13	2.47	9.23	2.24	10.66	
32.34	1.45	2.78	9.68	2.51	8.81	2.54	9.12	2.57	9.14	2.54	9.25	2.34	10.69	
42.65	1.53	2.91	9.69	2.66	8.83	2.62	9.12	2.74	9.15	2.69	9.27	2.47	10.72	
52.73	1.62	3.06	9.74	2.78	8.88	2.70	9.14	2.94	9.18	2.88	9.30	2.56	10.75	
62.59	1.73	3.27	9.77	2.90	8.93	2.79	9.17	3.01	9.21	2.98	9.32	2.70	10.77	
72.24	1.87	3.53	9.83	3.19	8.98	2.91	9.21	3.19	9.26	3.12	9.34	2.89	10.80	
81.69	2.06	3.78	9.89	3.36	9.04	3.09	9.24	3.37	9.32	3.35	9.39	3.12	10.83	
		L-Phenylalanine		Glycine			α -Alanine			L-Leucine				
		pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_z$	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_z$	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_z$		
0.0		2.25	9.18	2.35	9.59	5.38	2.36	9.71	5.44	2.39	9.61	5.24		
11.03		2.39	9.21	2.43	9.62	5.30	2.57	9.72	5.23	2.48	9.62	5.15		
21.80		2.51	9.23	2.53	9.64	5.20	2.76	9.74	5.04	2.58	9.63	5.05		
32.34		2.64	9.26	2.63	9.65	5.10	2.90	9.75	4.90	2.70	9.65	4.93		
42.65		2.76	9.30	2.76	9.72	4.97	3.04	9.78	4.76	2.83	9.66	4.80		
52.73		2.83	9.32	2.89	9.77	4.84	3.19	9.83	4.61	2.97	9.70	4.66		
62.59		2.91	9.36	3.04	9.80	4.69	3.31	9.86	4.41	3.19	9.76	4.44		
72.24		3.04	9.37	3.21	9.85	4.52	3.50	9.87	4.30	3.38	9.78	4.25		
81.69		3.16	9.41	3.49	9.91	4.24	3.74	9.90	4.06	3.60	9.81	4.03		

the 'medium effects', we prefer to work in dilute solutions where the errors due to salt formation, ion-pair formation must be very small. In mixed solvents, the activity coefficients change due to salt effect (f_i) and medium effect (m_i)²². In presence of neutral electrolytes, the solute-solvent interactions are likely to mask the 'medium effect' for the system considerably. Moreover, due to low solubility of amino acids in high percentages of organic solvents, it is desirable to work in dilute solutions and glass electrode can be suitably utilised for this purpose. Hepler and coworkers^{17,23-25} used the glass electrodes for the determination of the dissociation constants of weak acids and the autoprotolysis constants of water in different mixed solvents. The values of the dissociation constants of amino acids in water determined by us using glass-calomel electrodes agree well with those determined using H₂-electrode^{26,27}. In absence of data in mixed solvents, no comparison can be made. The change in pK values appear to be rational though the error in pK_2 values may be higher due to long time for equilibration in alkaline solution. Unstable emf readings in aqueous alkaline solutions have also been reported by Edsall and Blanchard²⁸. The pK_1 values of all the amino acids increase with the increase

in EG content in the mixture but the changes in pK_1 values are obviously different due to the changes in solute-solvent interactions of varied magnitude depending on the nature of the hydrophobic groups in the amino acid. It has been found that the changes in pK values are greater in EG + H₂O mixtures of relatively higher dielectric constants compared to those in other mono-ol + H₂O mixtures of lower dielectric constants⁴⁻⁶.

The pK_1 values are found to be linear functions of $1/\epsilon$ and the mole fraction of EG at low percentages but deviations occur at high percentages. Conversion of zwitterion to neutral forms with gradual addition of EG may be one of the reasons for deviations. But surely the conversion is very small²⁹ and is corroborated from the approximate estimates of

$$K_z = \frac{[\text{NH}_3^+ \text{RCO}_2^-]}{[\text{NH}_2 \text{RCO}_2\text{H}]}$$

K_z values in case of glycine, α -alanine and leucine were done in the way suggested by Edsall and Blanchard²⁸ (Table 2). The pK_E values for the esters of amino acids [$\text{N}^+\text{H}_3 \text{RCO}_2 \text{Et} \rightleftharpoons \text{NH}_2\text{RCO}_2\text{Et} + \text{H}^+$] have been assumed to remain

TABLE 3—FREE ENERGIES OF TRANSFER $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ VALUES OF AMINO ACID CATIONS

Wt% of EG	$G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$	Glycine	α -Ala-nine	L-Leu-cine	L-Va-line	L-Aspa-ragine	L-Serine	L-Glu-tamine	L-Methio-nine	L-Phe-nylala-nine
11.03	-0.63	-0.33	-1.38	-0.65	-0.69	-0.57	-0.27	-1.05	-0.07	-0.59
21.80	-1.10	-0.39	-2.74	-1.47	-0.64	0.04	-0.70	-1.52	-0.77	-0.51
32.34	-1.32	-0.44	-2.61	-2.09	-1.40	0.55	-1.19	-1.73	-1.02	-1.17
42.65	-1.64	-1.13	-2.17	-1.68	-2.01	0.42	-1.47	-2.40	-1.84	-0.97
52.73	-1.72	-0.78	-2.79	-2.30	-2.19	0.93	-1.54	-3.14	-2.81	-0.92
62.59	-1.79	-0.88	-2.96	-3.31	-2.76	1.08	-1.73	-3.20	-3.19	-0.97
72.24	-0.99	-0.28	-2.70	-3.26	-2.89	1.00	-1.06	-1.93	-3.05	0.07
81.69	-0.82	-0.06	-2.70	-3.54	-3.83	1.37	-1.17	-2.85	-3.32	0.32
In water :										
$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$	-1087.4									
$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$	-	-1 103.8	-1 102.4	-1 096.8	-1 100.0	-1 095.7	-1 098.1	-1 096.5	-1 096.8	-1 096.0

unaltered with changes in solvent composition. The low solubility of amino acids in mixed solvents compared to that in water also suggests that the predominant form of an amino acids is 'zwitterionic' in aqueous or mixed solvents.

The free energy changes (of dissociation) of amino acids as manifested in ΔG_i° (1) and ΔG_i° (2), have been found to be predominantly positive or unfavourable in going from water to mixed solvents. The contributory factors are the structural changes, the structure formation of water molecules due to the addition of ethylene glycol with two OH groups on one hand and hydrophobic interactions of amino acids and alcohols on the other hand. In order to get better insight into the nature of solute-solvent interactions, it is useful to analyse the results in terms of single ion values.

For reactions (1) and (2), we have

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$$

or

$$-\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm}) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(1) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$$

and

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{R}^-) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(2) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$$

The values of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{R}^-)$ have been calculated using the $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1)$, $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(2)$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ values from the present investigation and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values in ethylene-glycol determined by us³⁰. The values of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{R}^-)$

in water have also been calculated. The values are recorded in Tables 3 and 4.

Comparison of the transfer free energy changes of single ions is not possible due to non-availability of data in EG + H₂O mixtures but $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{R}^-)$ values have been found to be negative and positive respectively. The ΔG_i° values of halide and alkali metal ions in EG + H₂O mixtures have been reported to be consistently positive and negative respectively by Wells³¹ and Das and Kundu³² (The values reported by Das and Kundu are somewhat anomalous). The $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{R}^-)$ values of the amino acids are predominantly positive and increase continuously. Slight variations are observed in the region ~ 72 wt% ($X_2 = 0.43$). The $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ values are negative except for L-phenylalanine at high percentages and L-asparagine (from ~ 20 wt% of EG and onwards) if we consider values based on molarity. The $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ value of glycine becomes minimum at 42.65 wt%. The minima are at 21.8% for α -alanine, at 32 wt% for leucine and phenylalanine, at 62.6 wt% for serine, glutamine and methionine, at 11 wt% for asparagine. In case of L-valine, $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ decreases continuously. The reversal of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_2^{\pm})$ is expected in case of glycine and probably in case of α -alanine also. The $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ is negative and becomes maximum at about $X_2 = 0.3$ beyond which $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ increases and ultimately becomes positive near about 90 wt% (X_2

TABLE 4—FREE ENERGIES OF TRANSFER ΔG_t^0 (R^-) VALUES OF THE AMINO ACID ANIONS

Wt% of EG	Glycine	α -Ala-nine	L-Leu-cine	L-Valine	L-Aspa-ragine	L-Serine	L-Glu-tamine	L-Methio-nine	L-Phe-nylalanine
11.03	1.56	1.14	1.18	1.48	1.77	1.85	1.52	1.82	1.64
21.80	3.13	1.91	1.92	3.27	4.35	2.92	2.45	2.63	3.46
32.34	4.14	3.34	2.55	4.04	6.05	3.62	3.36	3.34	4.15
42.65	5.23	5.39	4.40	4.87	7.52	4.44	4.36	4.12	5.19
52.73	6.77	6.06	4.96	5.98	9.17	5.09	4.87	4.56	6.63
62.59	7.84	6.90	5.69	6.92	10.42	5.73	5.74	5.01	7.40
72.24	8.08	6.69	5.34	6.98	10.68	5.71	6.70	4.46	7.64
81.69	9.09	7.89	9.26	7.51	12.02	6.46	9.61	5.45	8.46
In water :									
$\Delta G^0(R^-)$	1 139.1	1 141.2	1 146.4	1 143.1	1 140.8	1 141.0	1 142.6	1 143.5	1 144.0

= 0.74) of EG, i.e. EG and EG-rich aqueous mixtures are less basic compared to water³⁰.

It is natural that the single ion values should be correlated to the structural variations of the solvent mixtures. It is well known that the structure of water is modified not only by EG but also by 'zwitterionic' amino acids with different hydrophobic groups. The calculations of excess thermodynamic functions of mixing of EG + H₂O mixtures by Wells³¹ shows that the excess free energy of mixing ΔG^E for EG + H₂O mixtures is slightly negative (almost zero) and is a smooth function of EG upto $X_2 = 0.3$ (minimum) but increases onward (ΔG^E +ve) and reaches a maximum at $X_2 = 0.6$. The ΔH_M^E and $T\Delta S^E$ are negative and changes continuously to reach minima at about $X_2 = 0.725$. Similar observations were made by Mazumdar and coworkers³⁰ from the excess relative permittivities $\epsilon_r^E(X)$ of the solvent mixtures. However, no ultrasonic absorption maximum is observed in EG + H₂O mixtures³¹. The structural changes appear to be well related with the acid-base properties of the solvent mixtures.

The basicity of the solvent mixtures have been observed by us to increase upto a region where the number of EG molecules is exactly half to those of H₂O molecules (when both solvents have equal number of OH group) due to increase in tetrahedral structure of water. However, as the number of OH group of the organic component increases, the basicity decreases due to gradual depolymerisation of tetrahedral structure of water releasing basic monomeric water free and the

basicity is reversed when the number of OH group of EG exceeds twice the number of OH group in water, e.g. above 77 wt% of EG. The result is in agreement with the observation of Frank and Ives³³. The hydrophobic group is considered to resist the pull into solution exerted by hydrophilic hydroxyl group which either as proton donor or acceptor can hydrogen bond with the solvent molecules. The second hydroxyl group in EG shifts the balance of competing influence in favour of aqueous behaviour.

Acid base properties are likely to change the equilibrium composition of the amino acid in solution (a mixture of zwitterion and cation or anion depending on the acidity or basicity of the solvent mixtures according to Scheme 1) which may be reflected in the ΔG_t^0 values of cations and anions of the amino acids.

The negative $\Delta G_t^0(RH_2^+)$ values can be ascribed to positive Born-type electrostatic interactions, hydrophobic interactions of variable magnitude and negative acid base interactions, whereas the positive values for $\Delta G_t^0(R^-)$ are due to Born-type electrostatic interactions, hydrophobic and hydrogen bonding as well as acid-base interactions.

It is desirable to analyse the error range of $\Delta G^\circ(\text{RH}_2^+)$ and $\Delta G^\circ(\text{R}^-)$ where errors are compounded from $\Delta G^\circ(\text{RH}^+)$, $\Delta G_i^\circ(1)$ or $\Delta G_i^\circ(2)$ and mainly from $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{H}^+)$. It is to be noted that the errors involved in $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{RH}^+)$, $\Delta G^\circ(1)$ or $\Delta G^\circ(2)$ may not be too large but nothing specific can be said about $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{H}^+)$. The $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values determined in EG + H₂O mixtures (0–100%) by us are usually in qualitative agreement with the few values reported by Das and Kundu³² (using the 'reference electrolyte' (TATB) method) but quantitatively the disagreement is about 1.0 kJ mol⁻¹. Our values are also in agreement with those reported by Wells³¹. Thus, the error range in the values of $\Delta G^\circ(\text{RH}_2^+)$ and $\Delta G^\circ(\text{R}^-)$ cannot be less than ± 1.0 kJ mol⁻¹ and the fluctuations of single ion values cannot be ruled out. It is to be noted that the 'single ion' values can only be obtained using 'extrathermodynamic' assumptions with inherent limitations and the values can never be absolute. It is thus desirable to use different methods and derive reasonably consistent set of single ion values. Considering the limitations, the results reported by us can be regarded to be fairly good particularly if we consider the observation by Popovych^{2,3} that an error to the extent of 2–3 kcal (g-ion)⁻¹ is usually associated with the single ion values of simple ions in water. Like Popovych and Tomkins² we also stress the need to determine the single ion values using different methods to extract more information regarding the structural aspects of solvent mixtures and ion-solvent interactions.

Experimental

All the amino acids used were procured from E. Merck, B.D.H., Sigma and Loba Chemie. The amino acids (except those of A.R. quality) were purified and estimated in the usual way. Ethylene glycol (G.R., E. Merck) was refluxed with Na-metal and finally distilled; the middle fraction was used for preparing the solution.

The experimental details for the determination of dissociation constants and solubility of amino acids were as described in our previous communications⁵⁻⁷. The calibration of the glass-calomel

electrode combination and the measurement of H⁺ ion concentrations in mixed solvents were performed as described in earlier communications⁵⁻¹³. The glass electrode was found to behave reversibly in EG + H₂O mixtures. However, the calibration was made before each set of measurements. Freshly distilled EG was used and the measurements made as early as possible to avoid probable polymerisation of EG in the mixtures leading to change in the pH-values. The pH-readings were taken using a Systronics digital pH-meter with combined glass-calomel electrodes maintained at 298 K. Spekol (Carl Zeiss, Germany) instrument was used for spectrophotometric estimations.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.C.D.) wishes to thank the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. Y. NOZAKI and C. TANFORD, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1963, **238**, 4074; 1965, **240**, 3568; 1970, **245**, 1648; 1971, **246**, 2211.
2. O. POPOVYCH and R. P. T. TOMKINS, "Non-aqueous Solution Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1981.
3. A. K. CHATTOPADHYAY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 930.
4. B. P. DEY, S. DUTTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 886.
5. A. PAL, B. P. DEY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 322.
6. S. K. CHAKRAVORTY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 399.
7. B. P. DEY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 136.
8. H. TALUKDAR, S. RUDRA and K. K. KUNDU, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1988, **66**, 461.
9. E. R. B. SMITH and P. K. SMITH, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, **117**, 209; 1937, **121**, 607, 1940, **132**, 47, 57.
10. J. G. KIRKWOOD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, **2**, 352.
11. L. G. UTERT and C. G. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
12. L. G. VAN UTERT, C. G. HAAS, W. C. FERNELIUS and J. E. DOUGLAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **75**, 455.
13. R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1973, pp. 276-278, 242-246.
14. U. C. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1966, **50**, 451.
15. S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 319.

16. H. M. N. IRVING and U. S. MANHOT, *J. Inorg Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1215
17. E. M. WOOLLEY, D. G. HURKOT and L. G. HEPLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 3908.
18. C. W. DAVIES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093.
19. J. P. GREENSTEIN and M. WINITZ, "Chemistry of the Amino Acids", Wiley, New York, 1961, Vol. I, Chap. 2.
20. N. DOLLET and J. JUILLARD, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 77.
21. Y. POINTUD and J. JUILLARD, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans 1*, 1977, **73**, 197.
22. Ref. 13, Chap. 8
23. E. M. WOOLLEY, J. TOMKINS and L. G. HEPLER, *J. Soln Chem.*, 1972, **1**, 341
24. E. M. WOOLLEY and R. E. GEORGE, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 119.
25. J. G. TREVERS, K. G. McCURDY, D. DOLMAN and L. G. HEPLER, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1975, **4**, 267
26. Ref. 19, Chap. 6.
27. S. GLASSTONE, "An Introduction to Electrochemistry", Van Nostrand, Princeton, 1942, p. 425
28. J. T. EDSALL and M. H. BLANCHARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2337
29. B. P. DEY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **27**, 979.
30. K. MAZUMDAR (née SENGUPTA), D. C. MUKHERJEE and S. C. LAHIRI, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1989, **142**, 1.
31. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1975, **71**, 1868
32. A. K. DAS and K. K. KUNDU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 467.
33. F. FRANKS and D. J. G. IVES, *Quart. Rev. (London)*, 1966, **20**, 1.
34. O. POPOVYCH in "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", 2nd. ed., eds. I. M. KOLTHOFF and P. ELVING, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1978, Part I, Chap. 12.